

LEARNING OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE AMONG MUSLIM MINORITY STUDENTS IN RELATION TO THEIR AGE AND GENDER

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Abstract

Today English is an international language, and it is also a link language. The importance of English has been increased in the present times. English language introduced us to the civilization of other countries, especially western culture. English has become an important element of contemporary Indian culture. English has proved as an effective system of communication. At the individual level, English is considered to be as a language, which provides opportunity of upward social mobility for people seeking advancement in the field of socio economic. It becomes a necessity for all the Indians to acquire the knowledge of English. The society of India is a multilingual, multicultural and pluralistic in nature. English is the most widely spoken language in India. It is used in different environment for different purpose for understanding the environment and to maintain the social activities; one has to make use of this language. In these days we recognize it as a library language because we get the treasure of tremendous knowledge through ancient books, and most of these ancient books present in English. In the global village, English Language has become the cardinal means of international affairs and communication. The use of the English Language is extended to the different fields of life and activities. The present study was conducted on 600 Muslim minority students from Hyderabad and Medchal districts of Telangana State. The result reveals that there was a significant difference in the learning of English language among the students with respect to age and gender.

Key Words: *English language, Residential Schools, Muslim Minority Students.*

Introduction: English is considered as an official language and is used as a link language among the states and countries as well as globally. It is the language of science, technology and business apart from being significant in political or diplomatic dialogues. English Language has come to be owned by all people in the world of work. Today the need of the hour is to be well versed in English language. In India, English is used in the process of communication with the outside world, It is also used for inter-state and intrastate communication with the advanced development in Information Technology, Science, Medical, Irrigation, Education, Mass communication, software and operating systems, a new utility for written and oral communication in the English language has emerged. English language is not only taught as compulsory subject at schools, colleges and universities but also used as medium of instruction. Hence teaching English language requires not only the skill, knowledge of subject, methods and strategies but also infrastructural facilities like language laboratory, teaching aids, teaching learning materials and teacher's resources books and audio-visual aids. The effective teaching and learning depends on use of suitable teaching aids and teachers competency.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study non English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in learning English language with respect to age.
2. To study non English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in learning English language with respect to gender.

Hypothesis of the Study

Hypothesis – 1: There exists significant difference between learning English language among non-English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in relation to their age.

Hypothesis – 2: There exists significant difference between learning English language among non-English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in relation to their gender.

Sample of the Study

Survey method was adopted. Sample was selected in two phases.

- ❖ Selection of districts
- ❖ Selection of students (8th Class)

Selection of districts: In Telangana there are 33 districts. Out of which two districts were chosen viz. Hyderabad and Medchal Malkajgiri.

Table: Showing selected sample “District wise”

<i>S.No</i>	<i>District</i>	<i>Number of Students</i>
1	Hyderabad	300
2	Medchal Malkajgiri	300
Total		100

Selection of students: Students were selected from 12 schools. From each school students studying in 8th class were selected. Thus, total students’ sample was 600.

Tool of the Study: Questionnaires were used to collect the data from the Muslim minority students in residential schools in Hyderabad and Medchal Malkajgiri districts of Telangana state. The questionnaires generated quantitative data but also provide qualitative data by eliciting the perceptions and opinions of the Muslim minority students. Pilot study was conducted before the final administration of the tool. Reliability and validity were established for the tool. In addition, this study also has taken into account the following secondary sources: official government data, existing academic literature and literature reviews, government Census report, Newspaper & Magazine reports etc.

Analysis and Interpretation

Hypothesis – 1: There exists significant difference between learning English language among non-English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in relation to their age.

Table 1: Showing Non-English medium Muslim minority students learning English language – age wise

Muslim Minority Students (Non English medium)	Age	N	Mean	SD	F	Sig.	Df
	10 – 12 Years	22	22.13	3.55	7.562	0.05*	2 & 597
	13 Years	103	23.27	3.28			
	14 Years and Above	475	25.45	2.75			
	Total	600	23.60	3.19			

**Significant at .05 level*

The mean score obtained for Muslim minority students with the age group of 10 to 12 years was 22.13, for the students with the age group of 13 years was 23.27 and for the students with the age group of 14 years and above was 25.45. The obtained F value 7.562 with a df of 2 & 597 was found to be statistically significant at .05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis 1, which states that ‘There exists significant difference between learning English language

among non English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in relation to their age’ is **accepted**. Therefore, it may be inferred that, Muslim minority students with the age group of 14 years and above were better than students with the age group of 13 years who in turn were better than the student teachers with the age group of 10 to 12 years in learning English language and it was statistically proved.

Hypothesis – 2: There exists significant difference between learning English language among non-English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in relation to their gender.

Table 2: Showing Non-English medium Muslim minority students learning English language – gender wise

Muslim Minority Students (Non English medium)	Gender	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig.	Df
	Boys	300	24.28	2.42	2.688	0.05*	1
	Girls	300	25.55	3.11			&
	Total	600	24.92	2.76			598

**Significant at .05 level*

The mean score obtained for boys was 24.28 and girls were 25.55. The obtained t value 2.688 with a df of 1 and 598 is found to be statistically highly significant at .05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis 2, which states that ‘There exists significant difference between learning English language among non-English medium Muslim minority students in residential schools in relation to their gender’, is **accepted**. Therefore, it may be inferred that, girls were better than boys in learning English language in residential schools in relation to their gender and it was statistically significant.

Findings

1. Muslim minority students with the age group of 14 years and above were better than students with the age group of 13 years who in turn were better than the student teachers with the age group of 10 to 12 years in learning English language.
2. Girls were better than boys in learning English language in residential schools in relation to their gender.

Conclusion

Learning English, today, plays a crucial role in our day to day lives. Earlier, students learn English not only as a language but also to score marks. Learning English benefits, the students to acquire the language skills and also helps them in their Professional advancement

and career growth. The result of the study reveals that there was a significant difference with respect to age and gender in learning English language in residential schools.

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